

Original article

Pointing correction based on limit cycles oscillators applied on a heliostats field digital twin[☆]Erick Vazquez^{a,*}, Alejandro Martínez-Hernández^{a,b}, Basharat Jamil^a, Milan Prodanovic^a, José González-Aguilar^a, Manuel Romero^a^a IMDEA Energy, Av. Ramon de La Sagra, 3, Mostoles 28935, Spain^b Senso Renoval, S.L. C/Aravaca N° 30, 28018 Madrid, Spain

A B S T R A C T

Digital twin models are an emerging topic that captures the dynamic response of physical systems to have a portrayal of digital representation. Complex systems such as heliostat fields for sustainable energy are good candidates for developing digital twins since the physical operation of facilities of this type can be highly time-consuming and weather-dependent. Therefore, a digital twin model of heliostat fields represents an adequate choice for the performance validation of new pointing correction algorithms with shorter assessing times. In this sense, one of the most important issues in the operation of heliostat fields for sustainable energy is to achieve a good accuracy of heliostats pointing to the target, even under physical errors of the solar field components and disturbances produced by external agents. However, since these types of disturbances have nonlinear characteristics, they should be dealt with by using nonlinear methods. This article presents a novel pointing correction technique based on nonlinear Limit Cycle Oscillators (LCOs) applied to the digital twin of a heliostat field. Analytical analysis, numerical verification, and further validation results are used to demonstrate the performance of the developed novel dynamic method.

Introduction

In recent years, the digitalization of new technology has served as a bridge between the data world and the physical world. This has helped to provide accurate virtual representations of complex dynamical systems called Digital Twins (DT) [1–4]. On the other hand, with the same development momentum, renewable electricity generation has been experiencing fast development and worldwide deployment [5–8]. Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) generation has also attracted significant attention as this technology is considered dispatchable employing thermal energy storage [9–10]. Solar tower or central receiver system (CRS) plants refer to one type of concentrating solar thermal power technology that uses 2-axes tracking mirrors, named heliostats, to direct the sunlight onto a solar collector or receiver located at the top of a tower [11–12]. In CRS-CSP plants, the pointing accuracy of individual heliostats on the solar receiver is crucial to maximizing solar energy collection, and consequently electricity generation, and ensuring safe operation [13]. This is particularly challenging since every heliostat has an image of the solar disk at the receiver that depends on sun/heliostat/receiver positions, sunshape (which could vary every day by light

scattering and attenuation in the atmosphere), heliostat structure and heliostat optical features [14].

Therefore, several simulation and prediction studies have been done to mitigate the impact of potential error sources, such as the sun position prediction, precision of the actuators that provide the heliostat movement, mechanical structure deformations, manufacturing tolerances, and heliostat relative position error [15]. For instance, ref. [16] compares different algorithms to determine with high accuracy the position of the sun; however, they use open-loop controllers unable to reduce the pointing error online. Geometrical errors that reduce heliostat tracking accuracy originated from three error sources (pedestal tilt, canting, and reference errors) have been addressed in [17]. Nevertheless, the parameters of the proposed method to minimize the pointing error require detailed experimental data from a whole solar year as the input of the optimization technique. For this reason, error sources introduced into heliostats tracking systems, arising from component limitations, construction, and placement, have been modelled employing digital ray-tracing techniques, reducing the error sources and time consumption [18–19]. However, the more accurate is, the more computational resources are required [16–20]. Therefore, a heuristic drift compensation

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method based on a polynomial approximation to the drift trajectories has been proposed to reduce software resources and improve heliostat tracking. Nevertheless, this calibration technique needs to be done by seasonal sampling [21]. Therefore, this technique could be performed in a digital twin model reducing the evaluation and verification times originated by the seasonal sampling. Other techniques to evaluate heliostat misalignments utilize detector arrays located on the tower, but they are unviable for high-power CRS plants due to the high temperatures and high irradiance generated in the tower [22].

Besides, some dynamic techniques have been developed as the one in [23], where an accurate adjustment of the heliostat is achieved by inducing mechanical oscillations in the heliostats. This vibration creates waves reflected from the heliostat in the target, which can be detected by sensors near the receiver target. Small deviations in heliostats can be adjusted once they are identified by Fast Fourier Transform analysis of the light waves received by the sensors. Unfortunately, this dynamic technique is affordable just for low radiation levels due to sensor material restrictions. Therefore, it can be seen that most of the pointing correction techniques are based on heliostat models that consider small structure misalignments and offset positions. However, dynamic techniques such as mechanical oscillations have not been broadly implemented.

In this context, this paper introduces and describes a novel dynamic technique of pointing correction for heliostat fields and solar towers based on nonlinear limit cycles. This method can be used to correct one-day pointing drift or offset by selecting an appropriate oscillation frequency. The main advantage of this dynamic method versus non-dynamic techniques has been addressed through the realization of the nonlinear limit cycle, which has been developed to compensate for disturbances as well as for the initial conditions. This makes it suitable to generate a closed orbit around a virtual center. Thus, this property combined with the digital twin model of the solar field, and a geometric recursive algorithm helps to reduce the offset while the heliostats are pointing to the solar tower and maximize the efficiency of the solar field automatically.

The next sections are organized as follows. An analysis of the dynamic system model of a Limit Cycle Oscillator (LCO) is developed in Section II. Section III shows the adaptation of the model for heliostat fields, and the limit cycle radius calculation is explored. Verification results on a heliostat field digital twin are depicted in Section IV to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed technique. An explanation of the discrete operation of the real VHCST and its digital twin is given in Section V. Finally, the conclusions are summarized in Section VI.

Limit cycle oscillators

Nonlinear synchronization methods are currently applied to synchronize periodic signals in oscillatory dynamic systems, being the so-called Limit Cycle Oscillators as one of the most relevant [24]. LCO has been identified as a robust technique against the disturbances caused by current and voltage controllers for grid-connected electronic inverters due to its circular symmetry around the origin. The presence of LCO decreases the ripple magnitude, increases the robustness, and reduces the distortion.

In this context, stable limit cycles are defined as the outcome of the dynamic evolution of the states of a two-dimensional dynamic system where the trajectories tend to form a closed orbit. An isolated periodic orbit is defined as a limit cycle [25]. The nonlinear self-sustained sinusoidal oscillation with this characteristic is described by the system of differential equations in polar coordinates below:

$$\dot{r} = \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{U_p} \right)^2 \right] r \omega \quad (1a)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = -\omega \quad (1b)$$

where r is the oscillation radius, U_p is the peak amplitude of the oscillation, and ω is the angular frequency. The dot over the variables means the derivative with respect to time. In other words, it means the rate of change of the variable over time. Eq. (1a) has three equilibrium points, one unstable at $r = 0$, and two stables at $r = \pm U_p$. Assuming that the radius is positive, the dynamic system can be written in cartesian coordinates as

$$\dot{x} = \omega \left(x + y - \frac{(x^2 + y^2)}{U_p^2} x \right) \quad (2a)$$

$$\dot{y} = \omega \left(-x + y - \frac{(x^2 + y^2)}{U_p^2} y \right) \quad (2b)$$

where x and y are two in-quadrature signals, and $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$. Fig. 1a shows the vector field (black arrows) given by Eq. (2) and the circular orbit of the radius U_p (blue line) as the corresponding limit cycle. Any trajectory (red lines) will evolve to the limit cycle regardless of its initial conditions. In fact, the Poincaré–Bendixson Theorem [26] shows that Eq. (2) has a closed orbit, which is named the Limit Cycle Oscillator (LCO). In contrast, a linear harmonic oscillator has a continuum of closed orbits, as shown in Fig. 1b, which do not allow for trajectory corrections. Therefore, the existence of a limit cycle allows the designing of control systems robust against trajectory deviations and initial condition errors.

Dynamic pointing correction based on LCO

Heliostat pointing is critical to ensure the performance of a heliostat field and becomes crucial in applications requiring high concentration with peaks flux from 3 kW/m² to 2500 kW/m², like high-temperature thermodynamic cycles, industrial processes, and solar fuels production. This is the case of facilities like the Very High Concentration Solar Tower (VHCST) located in Móstoles, Madrid, Spain (Fig. 2a) with a capacity of 169 heliostats distributed as in the diagram of Fig. 2c. All heliostats usually have small errors in their manufacturing process, tolerances, and small facet deformations due to their weight, which together with their position in the solar field lead to different flux map on the receiver. Moreover, uncertainties in the heliostat calibration and relative positions and local phenomena (like temperature) cause pointing errors [27] as the one depicted in Fig. 2b. Identifying individual pointing deviations during solar field operation is impossible due to the difficulties in distinguishing a single heliostat spot. However, as all these disturbances have nonlinear characteristics, they should be dealt by nonlinear tools to reduce their impact on the performance of the heliostat field. In this sense, a limit cycle with circular symmetry should be a good tool to correct heliostats pointing to a specific aiming point. Therefore, a procedure to implement a limit cycle for heliostat calibration purposes has been presently developed.

The calibration method proceeds in the following way. A specific heliostat h_1 aims at a set point on a target located in the tower as shown in Fig. 2b. Then, the two degrees of freedom of the heliostat (i.e. tilt and roll in the VHCST) are modified, so that the spot moves around its initial position (x_0, y_0) in accordance with the dynamics of the limit cycle (Eq. (2)).

Therefore, the heliostat spot will describe a transient trajectory from its initial position (x_0, y_0) towards the steady-state trajectory (red line) of the limit cycle (cf. Fig. 3a and b). If the heliostat does not properly aim at the requested set point, the circular trajectory of the heliostat spot will not be correctly aligned with the expected one (dotted blue line in Fig. 3a). It is important to highlight that this movement of the heliostat spot during and after the transient trajectory is following the nonlinear dynamic equation (2). That is, the nonlinear dynamic Eqs. (2a) and (2b) are processed to calculate the exact positions of the heliostat flux map over the target. It is important to understand that these equations do not

Fig. 1. a) Vector field of the limit cycle oscillator (Eq. (2)). Orbit of radius $r = U_p$ (Blue line). Possible trajectories inside and outside of the limit cycle (red lines). b) Vector field of a linear harmonic oscillator. Orbit of radius $r = U_p$ (Blue line). Closed trajectories remain at the same initial condition radius (red lines). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. a) VHCST facility consisting of 169 heliostats and main tower with one main target (location: IMDEA energy, Móstoles, Madrid, Spain). b) Pointing problem for heliostat h_1 . c) Solar field diagram. Red heliostat is the seventh heliostat of the sixth row (52nd, 7–6). Green heliostat is the seventh heliostat of the seventh row (64th, 7–7). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

describe the trajectory of the heliostat target but of the perturbation applied over the expected target. Such perturbation has its own radius and frequency.

Consequently, there were maximal (r_{max}) and minimal (r_{min}) radii between the stationary limit cycle trajectory (red line) and the center of the target (green dashed lines in Fig. 3b). Fig. 3c illustrates the distance from every point of the limit cycle to the set point as a function of time. It

is observed that the distance progresses following a sinusoidal function around the mean radius.

Since every point of the sinusoidal function in Fig. 3c corresponds to two symmetrical positions around the set point, it is straightforward that using the maximal and minimal radii allows to predict the value and direction of the offset δ needed to aim properly to the set point as it is depicted in Fig. 3d. It is important to mention that the value of the angular frequency (ω) should be a value sufficiently large for at least one full oscillation during the test. The offset δ is related to the offset in the x and y directions, δ_x and δ_y , respectively, as:

$$\delta^2 = \delta_x^2 + \delta_y^2 \quad (3)$$

Likewise, the maximum radius r_{max} and the minimum radius r_{min} are expressed as:

$$r_{max}^2 = x_{max}^2 + y_{max}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$r_{min}^2 = x_{min}^2 + y_{min}^2 \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, it can be seen in Fig. 4 that the offset δ can be written as a function of the maximum and minimum radii,

$$\delta = r_{max} - U_p \quad (6)$$

$$\delta = U_p - r_{min} \quad (7)$$

The oriented angle α is defined as the ratio of the corresponding x_{max} and y_{max} positions with the x - and y - directions offsets:

$$\tan(\alpha) = \frac{\delta_y}{\delta_x} = \frac{y_{max}}{x_{max}} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, replacing the offset δ of Eq. (3) in Eq. (6) results:

$$\delta_x^2 + \delta_y^2 = (r_{max} - U_p)^2 \quad (9)$$

An expression is obtained for δ_x by combining Eq. (8) and Eq. (9), and taking into account the solution with a positive sign, since the solution with a negative sign corresponds to the minimal radius case:

$$\delta_x = \frac{r_{max} - U_p}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{y_{max}}{x_{max}}\right)^2}} \quad (10a)$$

Besides, a similar formula can be found for the offset δ_y ,

Fig. 3. a) Transient trajectory of the deviated heliostat h_1 from the first position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (red line). b) Stationary limit cycle trajectory (red line) of the deviated heliostat h_1 . c) Maximal and minimal distances between points of the limit cycle and the target (Black dashed lines). Distance measures between every point of the limit cycle and the target (Black and green points). d) Direction and value of the offset needed to point with better precision to the target for heliostat h_1 . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

$$\delta_y = \frac{r_{max} - U_p}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{x_{max}}{y_{max}}\right)^2}} \quad (10b)$$

Furthermore, for the case with a minimal radius, the process of determining the offsets δ_x and δ_y uses Eq. (7) instead of Eq. (6) and it results in:

$$\delta_x = \frac{U_p - r_{min}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{y_{min}}{x_{min}}\right)^2}} \quad (11a)$$

$$\delta_y = \frac{U_p - r_{min}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{x_{min}}{y_{min}}\right)^2}} \quad (11b)$$

It can be seen that Eqs. (11a) and (11b) have solutions with a positive sign since the solution with a negative sign corresponds to the maximal radius case. Therefore, as it is depicted in Fig. 4, the brown dashed line is data from the nearest semi-arch to r_{max} , and the green dashed line is data from the nearest semi-arch to r_{min} . Thus, the offsets δ_x and δ_y can be written as functions of the orbit of the limit cycle U_p , the maximal (minimal) radius r_{max} (r_{min}), and the corresponding x_{max} (x_{min}) and y_{max} (y_{min}) positions.

Summarizing, Eq. (10) is used for the samples obtained through the semiarch of the r_{max} (Brown dashed semiarch of Fig. 4). Eq. (11) is used

for samples located in the semiarch of r_{min} (Green dashed semiarch of Fig. 4). The program decides which equation to use as a function of the resulting sign. Consequently, the solutions must always have a positive sign for the correct functioning of the algorithm.

Now, Eq. (10) and Eq. (11) need to be applied to every sample of the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map. Therefore, for n samples, the components of the offset calculation are:

$$\delta_x^{(n)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x,i} \quad (12a)$$

$$\delta_y^{(n)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{y,i} \quad (12b)$$

Moreover, in order to impose a convergence criterion, the change of the absolute value between the offset calculation given by $n-1$ samples and the next offset calculation given by n samples has been defined as:

$$\Delta\delta_x = |\delta_x^{(n-1)} - \delta_x^{(n)}| \quad (13a)$$

$$\Delta\delta_y = |\delta_y^{(n-1)} - \delta_y^{(n)}| \quad (13b)$$

$$\Delta\delta = \sqrt{\Delta\delta_x^2 + \Delta\delta_y^2} \quad (13c)$$

One important parameter of the dynamic pointing correction technique is the size of the limit cycle radius U_p , which must be positive since

Fig. 4. Geometric calculation of the offset δ in function of the limit cycle radius U_p , the coordinate position of the maximum radius (x_{max}, y_{max}) , and the coordinate position of the minimum radius (x_{min}, y_{min}) .

it is in the denominator of Eq. (2). An appropriate choice for U_p should ensure that the spot caused by the selected heliostat on the target is clearly distinguished from the main spot due to other heliostats. As a general rule, the minimum radius of the limit cycle $U_{p,min}$ must be higher than the radius at which the irradiance of the main spot is equal to one-half of the irradiance of the single heliostat under study.

Finally, Fig. 5 shows a flowchart of the dynamic pointing correction technique.

Experimental results

The dynamic pointing correction method was validated using a digital twin of the VHCST facility located in Móstoles, Madrid, Spain (40.339 N, 3.880 W). The VHCST consists of 169 heliostats and was specifically designed for high-temperature solar thermal applications.

The digital twin of the VHCST facility is a customized ray-tracing MATLAB® code that contains numerous parameters to describe any heliostat characteristic as well as the actual optical features of the facets. The digital twin has been validated using commercial ray-tracing software TracePro® and further validated with real data from the solar field [28]. The digital twin simulation tool outperforms the commercial software (TracePro®) in the simulation of the entire solar field by at least a factor of 10 regarding the computation time [29]. The advantage of using a customized ray-tracing digital twin to the real facility is the adaptive nature of the code that allows the simulations to be performed faster. This is attributed to the fact that the developed code makes use of Monte Carlo ray-tracing simulations to investigate and quantify all the disturbances in the heliostats pointing.

Therefore, each flux map is obtained through detailed Monte Carlo ray-tracing simulations. The simulations are performed by solving the tracking equations corresponding to a heliostat with a tilt-roll tracking system. The tracking equations are a function of the solar position (that depends on the latitude, azimuth, hour, and date), the spatial position of the heliostat, and the spatial position of the target. The solution of the tracking equations gives two angles, the roll angle, and the tilt angle. Once these two angles are known (σ and ϵ), the heliostat is oriented according to the next rotation matrices around the tilt and roll axes, respectively:

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the dynamic pointing correction technique.

$$M_\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos\sigma & \sin\sigma \\ 0 & -\sin\sigma & \cos\sigma \end{pmatrix} \quad (14a)$$

$$M_\epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\epsilon & 0 & \sin\epsilon \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin\epsilon & 0 & \cos\epsilon \end{pmatrix} \quad (14b)$$

Besides, for every misalignment of the heliostat structure that could produce pointing errors, the corresponding rotation matrices are also implemented in the ray-tracing code. In this way, the ideal heliostat orientation given by Eq. (14) is slightly modified, which introduces pointing errors in the simulations. Apart, the code also allows to take into account a constant pointing error with respect to the center of the target by introducing the offset δ employed in this study. For further information can be referred to [27].

For other heliostats with different tracking systems (azimuth-elevation, spinning-elevation, polar oriented, etc), the procedure would be similar, but with different tracking equations and different rotation matrices. Therefore, it is important to understand that the application of the Limit Cycle Oscillator could be applied to any type of heliostat because it is not linked with the motion basis of heliostats, and it is independent of it.

The heliostats selected to show and explain the process for determining the heliostat target points in the pointing correction based on LCO, were the seventh heliostat of the seventh row (named 7–7) and the seventh heliostat of the sixth row (named 7–6). These two heliostats have a focal length of 20 m, and 1 mrad and 1.3 mrad of mean optical error, respectively. These were specifically selected to compare the results between a quasi-circular well-defined spot (Heliostat 7–7) and a non-symmetrical spot (Heliostat 7–6).

All the simulations have been performed assuming a reflectivity of 90 %, and a Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) of 900 W/m². The dimensions of the heliostat facet are 1.6 m × 1.9 m, divided into squares of 2.5 cm, giving 4864 elements per facet. Also, the number of initial rays traced is fixed to 12.16 × 10⁶. Thus, the bundle of rays associated with the sunshape of each grid element consists of 2500 rays. Specifically for the heliostat 7–6, the matrices of slope errors (MSE) obtained by

Table 1

Test cases used in experimental results for dynamic pointing correction applied to the spot of heliostat 7–7.

Sam-ples	Recurrence: 5 min	Recurrence: 10 min	Recurrence: 20 min	Recurrence: 30 min
15	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
	$\delta_x = 23.87$ cm	$\delta_x = 23.97$ cm	$\delta_x = 23.74$ cm	$\delta_x = 24.12$ cm
	$\delta_y = 0.87$ cm	$\delta_y = 0.86$ cm	$\delta_y = 1.06$ cm	$\delta_y = 1.16$ cm
	$t_i = 13:37$	$t_i = 12:57$	$t_i = 11:37$	$t_i = 10:47$
20	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	
	$\delta_x = 23.39$ cm	$\delta_x = 23.49$ cm	$\delta_x = 23.53$ cm	
	$\delta_y = 1.38$ cm	$\delta_y = 1.88$ cm	$\delta_y = 0.87$ cm	
	$t_i = 13:27$	$t_i = 12:37$	$t_i = 10:57$	
25	Case 8	Case 9		
	$\delta_x = 24.11$ cm	$\delta_x = 24.31$ cm		
	$\delta_y = 3.65$ cm	$\delta_y = 3.76$ cm		
	$t_i = 13:12$	$t_i = 12:17$		

*Test date: 21–06–2023. Solar noon: 14:17. $U_p = 60$ cm. $\omega = 5.236 \times 10^{-4}$ rad/s. Real offset performed in tests: $\delta_{xreal} = 25$ cm, $\delta_{yreal} = 3$ cm. Absolute error: $\epsilon = |\delta - \delta_{real}|$

Table 2

Test cases used in experimental results for dynamic pointing correction applied to the spot of heliostat 7–6.

Sam-ples	Recurrence: 5 min	Recurrence: 10 min	Recurrence: 20 min	Recurrence: 30 min
15	Case 10	Case 11	Case 12	Case 13
	$\delta_x = 9.00$ cm	$\delta_x = 8.50$ cm	$\delta_x = 8.43$ cm	$\delta_x = 8.06$ cm
	$\delta_y = 7.93$ cm	$\delta_y = 7.75$ cm	$\delta_y = 7.68$ cm	$\delta_y = 7.93$ cm
	$t_i = 13:37$	$t_i = 12:57$	$t_i = 11:37$	$t_i = 10:47$
20	Case 14	Case 15	Case 16	
	$\delta_x = 8.38$ cm	$\delta_x = 8.10$ cm	$\delta_x = 7.64$ cm	
	$\delta_y = 7.04$ cm	$\delta_y = 6.58$ cm	$\delta_y = 6.35$ cm	
	$t_i = 13:27$	$t_i = 12:37$	$t_i = 10:57$	
25	Case 17	Case 18		
	$\delta_x = 9.13$ cm	$\delta_x = 8.67$ cm		
	$\delta_y = 4.60$ cm	$\delta_y = 4.37$ cm		
	$t_i = 13:12$	$t_i = 12:17$		

*Test date: 21–06–2023. Solar noon: 14:17. $U_p = 60$ cm. $\omega = 5.236 \times 10^{-4}$ rad/s. Real offset performed in tests: $\delta_{xreal} = 10$ cm, $\delta_{yreal} = 5$ cm. Absolute error: $\epsilon = |\delta - \delta_{real}|$.

deflectometry were employed, which makes it a very realistic digital copy of the physical system.

Table 1 and Table 2 summarise the two representative examples of experimental designs that consider 15, 20, and 25 samples with a recurrence between each sample of 5, 10, 20, and 30 min. It has been assumed that all the tests or cases have been made around the solar noon (local time, 14:17) on the summer solstice in order to have the lowest spot deformation between the first and the last sample.

It is also considered that a complete case is fully performed from sunrise to sunset. Therefore, the angular frequency (ω) has been selected to complete between 2 and 4 full oscillations per test for better results. That is $\omega = 5.236 \times 10^{-4}$ rad/s. Consequently, tests with 20 and 25 samples every 30 min as well as 25 samples every 20 min are discarded. For this reason, just 9 different cases with the above-mentioned parameters as shown in Table 1 are executed.

Moreover, the offset calculations δ_x and δ_y , and the initial times t_i and the final times t_f of the 9 test cases are shown in Table 1. Also, the absolute error (ϵ) has been depicted in Tables 1 and 2 with the respective real offset (δ_{xreal} and δ_{yreal}) performed through the tests. For the sake of economising the document extension, only the most representative cases (cases 4, 7, and 9) are presented to explain the results.

In this sense, it is depicted in Fig. 6 case 4 which consists of 15 samples with an occurrence of 30 min between them. Fig. 6a shows the 15 captures of the heliostat spot over the target, following the dynamic behaviour of the limit cycle along the time from 10:47 to 17:47. It is important to notice the deformation of the first and the last captures due to the time when they were made. This is due to a wide incidence angle between the sun-heliostat-target. This means, that the farther from solar noon, the more deformation the spot has. Moreover, it is shown in Fig. 6b the trajectory of the heliostat spot along the time from the initial time t_i , to the final time t_f . It can also be seen in this chart the first transient trajectory, and the one circular orbit where all the subsequent samples are contained.

Furthermore, Fig. 6c depicts the distance of the central spot to the origin (0, 0). Then, it can be seen an oscillation in the measurements of this radius. Therefore, the maximal radius r_{max} , the minimal radius r_{min} and their corresponding components (x_{max} , y_{max}) and (x_{min} , y_{min}) are

Fig. 6. Case 4. Dynamic pointing correction for heliostat 7-7. a) 15 samples with an occurrence of 30 min of the heliostat flux map from $t_i = 10$ h 47 m to $t_f = 17$ h 47 m. b) Trajectory of the centroid of the heliostat spot from the initial position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (blue line). c) Distance between the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map and the target position (0,0). d) Variation of the estimated offset $\Delta\delta$ and its components $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$ as function of the number of measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Case 7. Dynamic pointing correction for heliostat 7-7. a) 20 samples with an occurrence of 20 min of the heliostat flux map from $t_i = 10$ h 57 m to $t_f = 17$ h 17 m. b) Trajectory of the centroid of the heliostat spot from the initial position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (blue line). c) Distance between the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map and the target position (0,0). d) Variation of the estimated offset $\Delta\delta$ and its components $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$ as function of the number of measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

calculated in order to apply Eq. (10) and Eq. (11). It is important to notice that only the samples that are already in the limit cycle trajectory are used for the offset calculation (red line in Fig. 6c) since the samples that are in the transient trajectory are not possible to distinguish from the main spot.

Likewise, Fig. 6d depicts in redline the change of the absolute value between the offset calculation given by $n - 1$ samples and the next offset calculation given by n samples, $\Delta\delta$. It can be seen how the variation between every offset calculation decreases as the number of samples grows, which means a noticeable convergence of the technique. Moreover, it is elucidated in blue dotted lines in Fig. 6d, the change of the absolute value between the offset components calculation given by $n - 1$ samples and the next offset components calculation given by n samples, $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$. It can be seen that the offset component values have oscillations in their calculation. However, this fluctuation decreases as the number of samples increases, to a minimal convergence value which remains under $\Delta\delta$.

It is important to notice that the spot deformation has been reduced in case 7 and case 9, since the first and the last captures are closer to the solar noon than in case 4, as can be seen in Fig. 7a and Fig. 8a. In particular, case 7 and case 9 have 20 and 25 samples with a recurrence of 20 and 10 min, respectively. Moreover, in case 7, the samples of the first orbit intersperse the samples of the second orbit, without affecting the performance of the technique as can be seen in Fig. 7b. Furthermore, the radius measurement is not affected and the convergence improves slightly as the change of the absolute value $\Delta\delta$ is smaller than in case 4 as it can be seen in Fig. 7c and Fig. 7d, respectively. However, in case 9 the samples are captured almost in the same positions in every orbit due to the occurrence between the samples (cf. Fig. 8b). Also, the disturbance in the radius measurement is negligible (cf. Fig. 8c) and the convergence is better than case 4 and 7 since the change of $\Delta\delta$ is lower as it is depicted in Fig. 8d.

It is important to mention that heliostat spot 64th (7th heliostat, 7th

row) has an ideal spot shape symmetry. However, not all heliostats have this feature but have much more distorted spot shapes. For this reason, it is important to investigate the dynamic pointing correction technique with nonideal conditions to analyze the robustness of the method applied to nonideal spot shapes as the heliostat spot 52nd (7th heliostat, 6th row). Therefore, experimental tests have been made to heliostat spot 52nd with 15, 20, and 25 samples and a recurrence of 5, 10, 20, and 30 min. These experimental tests have been classified in just 9 different cases due to light hours restrictions, as is depicted in Table 2 (Case 10 to Case 18).

Fig. 9, Fig. 10, and Fig. 11 illustrate cases 13, 16, and 18, respectively, which are the most representative cases of the asymmetrical heliostat spot 52nd. Case 13 consists of 15 captures of the asymmetrical heliostat spot with an occurrence of 30 min, as shown in Fig. 9a. It is important to point out how the spot shape in Fig. 9a affects the orbit alignments depicted in Fig. 9b.

In the same way, the distance of the central spot to the origin (0,0) is also affected as shown in Fig. 9c. However, the convergence of the dynamic pointing correction technique is not perturbed as it is elucidated in Fig. 9d since the error associated to the samples before the solar noon counteract the error associated to the samples captured after the solar noon. Therefore, the samples of the first orbit counteract the samples of the second orbit in Fig. 9b.

This characteristic is present as well in case 16 (cf. Fig. 10) and case 18 (cf. Fig. 11), however, the anomaly is smaller than in case 13, since the recurrence between every sample is shorter, with 20 min for case 16 and 10 min for case 18. Moreover, this anomaly can be seen in Fig. 10b for Case 16 and in Fig. 11b for Case 18, and a clear deviation in the distance of the central spot to the origin (0,0) is found in Fig. 10c (Case 16) and Fig. 11c (Case 18). Nevertheless, the convergence is not clearly perturbed as the change in the absolute value $|\Delta\delta|$ is smaller than in Case 13, which can be seen in Fig. 10d (Case 16) and Fig. 11d (Case 18). In this case, there exists a similarity in the spot flux maps since the tests

Fig. 8. Case 9. Dynamic pointing correction for heliostat 7-7. a) 25 samples with an occurrence of 10 min of the heliostat flux map from $t_i = 12$ h 17 m to $t_f = 16$ h 17 m. b) Trajectory of the centroid of the heliostat spot from the initial position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (blue line). c) Distance between the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map and the target position (0,0). d) Variation of the estimated offset $\Delta\delta$ and its components $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$ as function of the number of measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Case 13. Dynamic pointing correction for heliostat 7-6. a) 15 samples with an occurrence of 30 min of the heliostat flux map from $t_i = 10$ h 47 m to $t_f = 17$ h 47 m. b) Trajectory of the centroid of the heliostat spot from the initial position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (blue line). c) Distance between the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map and the target position $(0, 0)$. d) Variation of the estimated offset $\Delta\delta$ and its components $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$ as function of the number of measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Case 16. Dynamic pointing correction for heliostat 7-6. a) 20 samples with an occurrence of 20 min of the heliostat flux map from $t_i = 10$ h 57 m to $t_f = 17$ h 17 m. b) Trajectory of the centroid of the heliostat spot from the initial position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (blue line). c) Distance between the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map and the target position $(0, 0)$. d) Variation of the estimated offset $\Delta\delta$ and its components $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$ as function of the number of measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Case 18. Dynamic pointing correction for heliostat 7–6. a) 25 samples with an occurrence of 10 min of the heliostat flux map from $t_i = 12$ h 17 m to $t_f = 16$ h 17 m. b) Trajectory of the centroid of the heliostat spot from the initial position (x_0, y_0) to the final limit cycle trajectory (blue line). c) Distance between the centroid of the heliostat spot flux map and the target position $(0, 0)$. d) Variation of the estimated offset $\Delta\delta$ and its components $\Delta\delta_x$ and $\Delta\delta_y$ as function of the number of measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

were performed with a small recurrence (10 min) over a short period of time (4 h) around the solar noon. However, still, sample 1 is quite different from the last samples.

Therefore, according to the absolute errors reported in Tables 1 and 2, the best accuracy of the present work is some tens of millimetres (Cases 8 and 17). This is one order of magnitude lower than passive methods reported in the literature (2 cm) [18–20].

Finally, some remarks can be made after examining the experimental tests. Firstly, the offset δ_{real} is the unknown value that the algorithm calculates. The variation of the estimated offset ($\Delta\delta$) decreases as the number of samples increases. This shows that the algorithm converges to an estimated offset (δ) as can be seen in Figs. 6–11(d). In other words, there is no change between the estimated offset (δ) with $n-1$ samples and the estimated offset (δ) with n samples. Consequently, the more samples are captured, the better the precision of the technique is. Moreover, the closer the initial and final samples are to the solar noon, the less deviation in the orbits they have. This is because the error associated with the samples before the solar noon counteracts the samples captured after the solar noon. Lastly, the spot shape has a minor impact on the performance of the convergence of the dynamic pointing correction technique.

Field implementation aspects

The field application of the proposed technique is intended in future. However, preliminary studies are in preparation for the algorithm's practical implementation and operation. To obtain the results for this paper all the studies were performed offline. All the parameters of the heliostat field are preloaded for the date and time required for the optimization since they are based on already gathered and known data. Geometric and optical attributes of the heliostat have been characterized and loaded before the simulations, while the positions of the heliostat

and sun are in function of the date and time of the correction tests.

Computational efficiency, measured in the time required to perform a simulation (10 s–20 s), is sufficiently fast for the calculation of the online pointing calibration. This is because the sun's position change is negligible over such a short period. In fact, the VHCST has a latency of 10 s between every correction of the heliostat pointing. It is important to point out that in practical implementation the heliostat tilt-roll movement is not continuous but is discrete (defined by steps). Therefore, the proposed technique is applicable taking these considerations into account.

Conclusion

In this paper, a novel dynamic pointing correction technique for heliostat fields based on nonlinear limit cycle oscillators has been proposed. Analytical analysis together with numerical verification, and further validation applied on a digital twin of a specific VHCST facility show the robustness of the technique under non-ideal spot shapes. The advantage of this technique is that it does not use any detector array located on the solar tower. Also, the computing cost is very low compared with commercial software, which makes it feasible to perform pointing correction in real time. Moreover, the performance of the convergence of the technique is in the function of the modulation of the number of samples and the occurrence between them. That is, the more samples are captured, the better precision the technique has. Likewise, the closer the initial and final samples are to the solar noon, the less deviation in the orbits occurs. Finally, it has been shown that the spot shape has a minor impact on the performance of the convergence of the present technique. For future work, it is thought to apply the proposed technique to correct the heliostats pointing in real-time control prototypes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Erick Vazquez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Alejandro Martínez-Hernandez:** Software. **Basharat Jamil:** Writing – review & editing. **Milan Prodanovic:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **José González-Aguilar:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Manuel Romero:** Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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